

Cybercrimes : Triumph of Conviction – Paucity of Jurisdiction

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Abstract

The modern era is electronic era. The electronic plays a very significant role in our day-to-day life. Amongst them one is the internet. Legal and regulatory parts of internet are something which is emerged by cyber law. Any legal issues or any such legal aspects related to the “Netizens”¹ are administered by cyber laws. To be specific cyber laws established all the legal issues related to the use of internet by people in the cyberspace. The cyberspace users are gradually increasing day by day all over the world and this has also resulted in vulnerability of cyberspace from all perspectives. Cybercrimes can be plainly understood as outlawry which is related to a computer or involves a computer. It can be understood that a criminal activity done with the help of a computer can be termed as Cybercrime. This is done generally to damage the reputation of person or a group of persons by using internet or other telecommunication mechanisms. The cybercrimes are not confined to a limited boundary. It is a cross-boundary problems. A person may commit an offence by sitting from remote part of any geographical area but it can harm throughout the world. In that circumstances it is very difficult to determine the jurisdiction for the conviction. The States are sovereign and they will claim their jurisdiction to punish the culprit. The jurisdiction issue is one of the great challenges before the world community. The damage can be both physical and mental and a person gets equally affected by such criminal activities. Periodically the estimated graph of cybercrime is rocketing upwards and people are further prone to it for which each one is using their own innovation for getting protection and security over cyberspace. This has many merits and demerits. This paper aims to examine the effects of cybercrimes and analysing the conviction of it.

Key words: Cybercrimes, Cyberspace, Internet, Innovative, Triumph of Conviction, Jurisdiction.

Introduction

In the contemporary world internet plays a pertinent role in each and every one life and being deprived of computers is functioning they became handicap. But there are numerous numbers of major issues that have become an obstacle in the pathway of success of cybercrimes. In absence of jurisdiction there is a resolute nonattendance in the imperative role for making any criminal triumph of conviction in cybercrimes. The authority plays significant facet for construction any process for rewarding. On the contrary cyber outlawry cases have made it very tough for the officers who are investigating such cases. There are several disparities in dealing with such cases as it would not be able to outlined the specific territorial competencies of any cybercrime. It defines *cybercrimes as “whoever knowingly something that conceives, conceals, destroys, alters, knowingly or intentionally causes other to destroy, alter or conceal any computer source document used for a computer, computer program, computer system or computer network when the computer source code is required to be kept or maintained by law for the time being in force shall be punishable with a fine which may extend up to rupees two lakh rupees or imprisonment up to three years or with both”*². Pornography, fraud transactions, sending threatening emails, sexual harassment, phishing, hacking anyone's account etc. are some of the common examples of cybercrimes³.

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The inquest being if someone sitting in foreign waters commits a cybercrime in India then in what footing can India bind them for conviction? The proportion of conviction in such cases in India is 0.5%, even if a police officer swiftly responds to a complaint the websites denial to co-operate creates a negative situation. Hence, Jurisdictional hindrances in cyberspace have reasoned a poor conviction rate in such cases.

Conviction of Cybercrime Cases

In the era of computers, it is very obvious that there has been a blaring progress in existing crimes. It is evident that to curb down cyber offences in India, we got a specific statute to adjudicate particularly for cybercrimes on 17th October 2000⁴ ie., The Information Technology Act, 2000. The Act intended to adjudicate such crimes which are committed with the aid of computers and internet. It is very surprisingly, since 2008, it is found that there has been a shocking increase in the internet dishonesties which has developed in full-fledged across the universe. Nevertheless, dreadfully, if hundreds of cases of cybercrime have been reported but only 40 cases have been responded.

The fruitage is that this type of crimes is less theoretical and has a brilliant repayment making it tireless for an investigating officer of police department to determine an evidence and present it before the court of law. Analysing the urging quota under cybercrimes, the condition is melancholic. The lucrative persuasion is steered by a fruitful inquiry with sufficient and relevant evidences. The present situation is also depicting that the conviction rate in cybercrime has elevated since previous period but even today due to scarcity of sustenance and well-defined laws the hindrances of attesting a criminal act existing even today. The main cause for such rise in cybercrimes is that it is shallow to infiltrate but burdensome for implementation of law and achieve persuasion.

Customarily, it is considered as a "white collar" offence and the person committed an offence is considered to be one with a delinquent behaviour than a felonious. This leads to make an insignificant person recognise that an unusual search agency is not well prepared and well adapted with cybercrimes. It is well established fact that and it is stated that "*In criminal Justice system, investigation into the crime and collection of evidence is of little consequence unless the prosecution is able to secure conviction of the accused. If the investigating agency unable to get the accused convicted by the court, it has a damaging impact on the investigating agency and it creates suspicion about the motive and capability of the investigating agency.*"⁵

In the above analysis, a proposition that should be splashed for tackling the concern of low conviction rates embroils:

1. It providing competent tool to the law prosecution authorities.
2. Apart from the major cities, cybercrime compartments required to be established in all the towns.
3. Trained the government officials in Computer and Forensics techniques.
4. It is required for trained and expert Information Technology advocates and Judges.
5. There is requirement of well deep-rooted technique for analysing with cybercrime matters on a priority manner.

It is very pertinent to mentioned here that the observation made by Mr. Talwar in this regard. He states that "*We need to ensure cases so as to tackle them that we have specialized procedures for prosecution of cybercrime on a priority basis. This is necessary so as to win the faith of the people in the ability of the system to tackle cybercrime. We must ensure that our system provides for stringent punishment of cybercrimes and cyber criminals so that the same acts as a deterrent for others.*"⁶ It is very significant to examine here that the paramount part in getting persuasion is bestowing of indication against the person committed an offence it proved only with strong and powerful technological aids to be used for demonstration.

The Rate of Successful Conviction of Cybercrimes

There are revealing matters related to cyber offences, where there has been a successful conviction in cybercrimes matters. It is very pertinent to discuss a landmark case on cybercrimes. From time to

time the court laid down various principles through the judicial pronouncement.⁷ The facts of the case were that, A person posted an offensive, annoying and scandalous communications to a divorcee. The culprit person generated a bogus electronic mail account in the name of divorcee women to harass her by sending a huge electronic message to her. Meanwhile, the electronic messages were mailed in the platform of yahoo messenger and it caught the eye of people at large number within a fraction of time. She begins to receive unwanted and unknown phone calls from strangers as they believed that she was responding their calls. Consequently, she lodged a complaint on February, 2004 in the Chennai Cyber-cell. The complaint was lodged under the Act.⁸ The culprit was caught by the police personnel of cybercrime cell in Mumbai after passing of long days. The culprit promised that lady to marry her. The women on believing him, she gets rid out of marriage relationship with her husband. After divorce, he denied to marry that women but used her to get pleasure from her end.

In another case in *Avnish Bajaj v. State* (Baazee.com case)⁹ the court detailed discussed the matter of cybercrimes. The fact of the case was that “baazee.com” was an auction site whose Chief Executive Officer, Mr. Avnish Bajaj was arrested for distributing child pornography materials with the help of his website. It was also found that there was some Multimedia Messaging Service (MMS) advertisement viz., “DPS Girls Having Fun”.

That the Outlets in the Statute are Perceived as Perks by the Delinquent

The primary aims of the Act is “To provide legal recognition for transactions carried out by means of electronic data interchange and other means of electronic communication, commonly referred to as ‘electronic commerce’¹⁰. It consists the regulating of substitutes to physical paper-oriented means of message and gathering of evidence, minimise which enable automated institution of credentials to the authorities as well as it enables to amend the certain provisions of penal laws in India¹¹ and matter relating to evidences.¹² At the same time, it also aims to bring some amendment in the Banking evidence¹³ and the Banking system in India¹⁴ which are directly or indirectly interlinked with cybercrimes.

The Act¹⁵ mainly discusses with varied crimes and consequences concerned with computer lawlessness nevertheless anyway, it helps to point out variety of reducing slabs. Although, it is a preliminary statute that very clearly discusses with cyber laws that governs very varieties of provisions. Some of them are described below:

1. The Act¹⁶ contains 94 sections and it is divided in 13 Chapters, although bulk of these sections deal with a chow of bolstering e-commerce. Cyber offences are penalised unilaterally in two chapters particularly 9 and 11.
2. Section 79, however does not penalise Intermediaries outlined in a few cases.
3. Pornography by Indian Websites is scrupulously contraband. Nonetheless, Foreign websites are free to promulgate such data unaddressed by the Act.
4. The Police, as outlined by the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973¹⁷ is restrained to examine any Private Property in the absence of a warrant. Cyber outlaws predominantly operate from their homes, where the police lack power.

That there is Scarcity of Jurisdiction¹⁸ under Matters of Cyber Crime

Jurisdiction establishes the physical authority accepted to a legally created legal thing. Its jurisdiction can be categories in the following two:

1. *Subject Matter Jurisdiction*: Implying that Jurisdiction of a Court over a peculiar subject matter. It has to be resolved that whether a claim is actionable before the court or not, and
2. *Personal Jurisdiction*: Also christened as “*In Personam Jurisdiction*”¹⁹. Any person involved in a civil suit is constrained to follow the decisions of that particular court whose jurisdiction befalls. Not every court can exercise its jurisdiction over any person who does not fall in the territory of the same or has any manifestation with that.

No doubt, as far as concerned the Jurisdiction over Internet is one of the greatest challenging tasks before the international community. As we know that still we do not have an established laws in this

regard. It is need of our to settled the cyberspace jurisdiction. Unless and until we are getting a settled laws on jurisdiction over internet, we would not be able to solve the matters of cybercrimes. I would like to quote an observation made by Mr. Talwant Singh in this regard. He stated that *“As long as different countries have different laws and cultures, there are no good principles for jurisdiction. Only ones have. All nations want unity but no one wants to give up its traditions”*²⁰

In this regard it is very significant to mention a famous case in these issues is *Cybercell Inc. v. Cybersell*²¹ The fact of this case was that there was disagreement amid the two companies.²² Their dispute is related to service marks between these two corporations. It was observed by the court that the outcome of trial cannot be applied in the same manner to a corporate body as it is applied to a separate entity or person. The court observed that *“it is because a corporation does not suffer harm in a particular geographical location in the same sense that an individual does.”*

Indian Extradition Practice in Case of Cybercrimes

The term extradition²³ is defined as *“The surrender of a criminal by a foreign state to which he has fled for refuge from prosecution to the state within whose jurisdiction the crime was committed upon the demand of the latter state, in order that he may be dealt with according to its law”*²⁴

There are many conventions in cyber laws which helps to extradite cybercrimes. These Conventions are supported by the international laws or international customary laws which permits to extradite and it includes search, seizure and conviction too. In this at this juncture it is very pertinent to mention the observation made in *Rambabu Saxena v. State*²⁵ by the Supreme Court of India. It very aptly observed that *“India is still not signatory to these treaties which has been signed by over 50 countries and do not mention cybercrime an extraditable offence. But it may not deter the Indian Government from granting extradition that if the treaty does not enlist a particular offence for which extradition was sought, but authorizes the Indian government to grant extradition for offences by inserting a general clause to this effect, some extra extradition may still be granted.”* Nevertheless, the problem related to extradition remains the same as the legislations of the European Union forbid not only its own nationals but also, persons, of any nationality, wanted by any country, for extradition, which award the capital punishment for such crimes.²⁶

Special Judge observed that *“Till date, we do not have a single treaty with any other country to extradite a cybercriminal to be brought to India He said India has physical boundaries in terms of its geographic location with other countries, but there was no such boundary”* at the cyber domain. *“Our cyber boundary is not (yet) defined. We have to protect our cyber boundaries also”*²⁷

Now, praiseworthy to mention here that there is a single case even today, India with very high expectation deliver a letter to United States of America to Rogatory as an earliest possible with the help of website of Maharashtra Government which was immediately hacked. Thanks to Government that suddenly traced the drudge's Internet Protocol (IP) site and that was caught as the in the America. Nonetheless even today, the America did not share any evidence. In these circumstances, it can be clearly understood that India failed to resolve the jurisdictional problems unless and until the concerned countries are entering into extradition treaty.

Conclusion

From the above discussion we can conclude this discourse in that way that cybercrimes have invented as one of the acute difficult troubles with cybercrimes are very differently those crimes that are omitted with the aid of computers and internet. Every side of cybercrime is regulated through the Information Technology Act, 2000, in the present time this is sole statute in India which regulates the act of cybercrimes. It is submitted that there is an urgent need of a stringent law which govern the cases of cybercrimes.

It is also drawn an attention that in our country there is urgent needs to be established a cyber-cell in each and every State, it may help to sort out the problems of cybercrimes. In the age of globalisation and modernisation technology is playing a vital role in giving the shape of the modern life style and is fully techno-friendly, and every care must be taken by the police personnel. The modern police personnel must be efficient, well-equipped with the modern computer gadgets and must be expertise in the fields of cybercrimes, because no doubt it is entirely different from conventional criminal

activities. But at the same time, it is also appreciable that in many parts of the States the existing cyber-cells are successfully in convicting the wrongdoer but in spite of that it is also experienced that the conviction rate is very low. We are experiencing that in India it is also undeniable fact that the rate of conviction in matters of cybercrimes is comparatively very less, or we conclude that the conviction rate in the matter of cybercrimes, even it is less than twenty-five per cent entire cases being reported. It is found that there are numerous reasons for such a failure as far as concerned in the conviction of accused in cybercrimes matter is the determination of problems of jurisdiction in the cyberspace. As we know that cyberspace is not restricted or confined by any geographical area or pecuniary adjudication. At the end it is submitted that to curb down the cybercrimes, it very significant to established its jurisdiction and competencies to adjudicate the cybercrimes. There is an urgent need of clear and stringent laws to regulate the cyberspace and cyber-offences.

References:

- 1 Generally, a user of the Internet, especially a habitual or keen one. ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Netizen) Netizen)
- 2 The Information of Technology Act, 2000, Section 65.
- 3 *Ibid.*, Chapter XI
- 4 The Information of Technology Act, 2000.
- 5 See., for details., Overhaul in Investigation and Prosecution of Cyber Crimes in India; Mr. Barun Kumar Sahu
- 6 Cyber Law and Information Technology; Mr. Talwant Singh
- 7 *State Of Tamil Nadu v. Suhas Katti* ; (CC No. 4680 of 2004)
- 8 The Information Technology Act, 2000, Section 67.
- 9 150 (2008) DLT 769
- 10 Transactions carried out by means of electronic data interchange and other means of electronic communication, commonly referred to as "electronic commerce" IT Act, 2000
- 11 Indian Penal Code, 1860
- 12 Indian Evidence Act, 1872.
- 13 Bankers Books Evidence Act, 1891
- 14 Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934
- 15 Information Technology Act, 2000
- 16 *Ibid.*,
- 17 Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973
- 18 In Latin 'jus', 'juris' means "**law**" and 'dicere' means "to speak"
- 19 Courts have to determine **personal** rights and liabilities of the parties before it
- 20 Jurisdictional issues in Internet Disputes; Mr. Talwant Singh
- 21 1997 US App.
- 22 One is Orlando and other is Arizona.
- 23 The action of extraditing a person accused or convicted of a crime from to one country to other
- 24 Black Law Dictionary, <http://thelawdictionary.org/extradition/>
- 25 AIR 1950 SC 155
- 26 Information Technology Law and Practices; Mr. Vakul Sharma
- 27 The Central Bureau Investigation Special Judge, New Delhi, Mr. Talwant Singh

